

REPORT

STATUS REPORT FOR DIGITAL LIFE NORWAY

April 17, 2024

Scientific Advisory Committee

Digital Life Norway

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1 INTRODUCTION

The DLN is an ambitious and large-scale initiative by the Norwegian Research Council. Its aim is to transform Norway's economy with an innovative approach based on transdisciplinary science and technology combined with a novel framework of responsible research and innovation (RRI). The missions of the DLN are first to become a nationally and internationally visible centre that can leverage synergies between existing biotechnology R&D capabilities of the Norwegian research landscape and second to create a robust knowledge base for the future. In order to achieve this the DLN brings together research groups and research fields forming genuinely novel collaborations and catalysing innovation relevant to the challenges of the Norwegian economy.

During the last funding round, the NFR has funded six new projects with a budget of typically NOK 20 million. Altogether, there are now 12 projects funded under the DLN umbrella. There is a large diversity of topics within DLN-funded projects, ranging from digital salmon to a project aimed at producing cement using microbes. The unifying theme in the centre is the transdisciplinary nature of all projects. There is also one project focusing exclusively on responsible research and innovation (RRI).

All these projects include genuine collaborations between wet-lab scientists and mathematical/computational modelers. The DLN is thus becoming a beacon of transdisciplinary research in Europe.

This short report prepared by the Scientific Advisory board of the DLN will briefly comment on aspects of the centre that are related to the scientific production of the centre, in the widest sense. The primary aim of the report is to give advice in response to discussions with the centre management and to compile observations and suggestions for improvements on the initiative of the SAB.

2 CRITERIA FOR SUCCESS

With an initiative of the size of the DLN it is necessary to define appropriate measures of success. It will be important not to reduce success criteria to simplistic quantitative measures which would only obfuscate the real achievements of the centre (or lack thereof). Instead the criteria should enable a balanced judgement of the degree to which the centre has reached its potential and ambition. The evaluation should concern both the individual projects and the centre as a whole. Given the nature of DLN, it is likely that a full evaluation of the impact and benefit of the centre cannot be given immediately, i.e. following the initial 5 year period

of the centre. A full picture of the effect of the centre will materialise on a longer time-scale.

2.1 Performance criteria for individual projects

In addition to the well established NFR performance criteria, the following impact measures may be specifically relevant to DLN projects:

- To what extent DLN researchers have progressed their career in industry and academia.
- Number of start ups/spin-off that have been created within 5 years of project completion.
- Follow-up funding and opportunities (new collaborations etc..) of DLN projects once completed.

2.2 Performance criteria for the centre as a whole

When evaluating the performance of the centre as a whole, it will be important to refrain from reducing the evaluation to simple quantitative measures. The achievements of the centre will be better captured by an overall narrative, rather than by numbers alone. A difficulty in the evaluation will be to identify the marginal effects that are directly attributable to the centre. Aspects to be taken into account when evaluating the centre include:

- Creation of synergies and new collaborations between projects.
- The extent to which the DLN has transformed the Norwegian R& D landscape beyond the projects that have been funded. How has the example of the DLN led to a change in research culture?
- The degree to which the knowledge and skill base of the Norwegian economy, especially the transdisciplinary skill-base has increased.
- The extent to which an increased flow of knowledge and skill between academia, industry and other stakeholders is directly or indirectly attributable to the DLN.
- The causal effect of the DLN on the creation of a research culture that rewards responsible, relevant, reflexive and societally aware science and technology production.
- The ability of the centre to facilitate international cooperations.

2.3 Evaluation of a research strategy based on RRI

The framework of responsible research and innovation is central to the idea of the centre. While also widely adopted elsewhere, it should be noted that RRI has itself not been evaluated. The evaluation of the DLN will be a welcome opportunity to understand whether RRI is useful. Two questions will need to be addressed: *(i)* Have researchers genuinely engaged with and internalised RRI, or has this remained a marginal activity that was largely not integrated with the technical parts of the projects? *(ii)* Is it possible to identify added value of RRI activities? Is there evidence that the inclusion of RRI in the projects has led to more robust science and technology outcomes with better value for society? *(iii)* Is it possible to attribute positive effects of the DLN directly to RRI activity? *(iv)* Was the RRI value for money, or would it have been better to spend the money on additional research projects?

3 INTERNATIONAL SIGNIFICANCE AND VISIBILITY

DLN is first and foremost of national importance in Norway, in that its mission is about enhancing the capabilities of Norwegian biotechnology research. Internationalisation is therefore not an aim in itself, except if it is subservient to the national mission. From this one can derive relevant objectives for the internationalisation strategy:

- Enhance the national skill-base by adopting new skills and good practice from abroad.
- Access European and international resources and competence.
- Access European and international funding and research collaborations to enhance and complement DLN funding.
- Attract new talents, scientist, entrepreneurs to enhance and complement the Norwegian landscape.

These aspects of international collaboration can be achieved at the level of the individual projects. Current projects include strong international collaborations. PIs of the individual projects are already leading figures in their field with extensive contacts outside Norway.

At the level of the centre, there are additional opportunities for internationalisation, including:

- The centre has significant funding and is as such an international player. It can and should influence international funding priorities in line with the priorities set by the NFR and the centre goals.

- The centre will act as a natural point of contact with international companies and businesses that wish to invest in/interact with the Norwegian research community. A coordinator should be appointed to facilitate this. The webpages should have a dedicated area for interested businesses.
- Early career researchers (ECR) and PhD students should be given the opportunity to spend some time at partner institutions abroad. This could be either in the form of internships in companies or in research institutions.
- The SAB is a point of contact for internationalisation. In particular, it has the potential to become a partner for international businesses that wish to collaborate with Norwegian science and technology. This aspect of the DLN is currently under-developed.

4 TRANSDISCIPLINARITY, TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT

An important mission of the DLN is to break up the compartmentalisation of Norwegian research along the boundaries of traditional disciplines, between academic and industrial research and between applied and fundamental research. Substantial progress has already been made by the DLN to promote a new research culture. In order to achieve lasting success more efforts are required. In particular, a big obstacle for the development of a new type of transdisciplinary researcher are the existing career paths. Existing academic structures encourage specialisation and discourage responsible research. Changing this is beyond the scope of the centre, but the DLN can make contributions.

In particular, the DLN can support the career and skills development of early career researchers, students and other project participants who do not have permanent contracts. The SAB notes that some efforts have been made to achieve this. The DLN is organising 13 workshops and training events in 2017, many of which are aimed at ECRs and PhD students. The SAB recommends a number of further mechanisms:

- Encourage participation of ECRs in international competitions, such as iGEM and similar events.
- PIs and the centre as a whole should support ECRs in actively contributing and shaping DLN arrangements (such as the annual conference), but also external activities, including as invited speakers, longer-term visits abroad, membership of program committees and journal editorships.

- Dedicated micro-projects that allow ECRs to gain first experience in project management.
- Consider innovative forms of PhDs, for example industrial PhDs with a 4th year in the biotechnology industry instead of teaching.
- Mechanisms to support community building within the project, especially for early career researchers and research students. These could include:
 - Annual social program for ECRs and students of DLN (“fishing in Lofoten”)
 - Collaborative mini-projects between existing DLN projects. This could be small amounts of funding to buy equipment or support inter-site travel to support emerging collaborations between project participants, especially young participants.

5 WHAT SHOULD BE HIGHLIGHTED IN THE NEXT DIGITAL LIFE CALLS TO ALLOW THE BEST POSSIBLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CENTRE?

The SAB notes that there is no clear common theme between all the projects. While all projects rely on a combination of wet-lab and *in silico* methods, there is no thematic thread that combines them. Consequently, PIs may disengage with centre activities, which would threaten the overall mission of the DLN to create a community of new researchers across Norway.

The SAB noted that the centre leadership has no influence over the projects that are to be funded. This makes it difficult to realise a long-term strategic vision for the centre as a whole. To overcome this problem, the centre leadership should be given the ability to steer the thematic focus of the centre. While scientific excellence of projects must remain the prime criterion of the selection of future projects, additional mechanisms may be used to encourage high quality submissions in areas where the centre leadership identifies a strategic need for DLN. Future calls for research projects could then, for example, be focussed on narrow areas. The scientific leadership of DLN should be allowed substantial input in the drafting of the call and the the project selection criteria.

An attractive option to manage the internal composition of the DLN is to include existing NFR-funded projects under the centre umbrella. The centre leadership should take a pro-

active approach and identify candidate projects and approach them. This will be most successful if the DLN could offer some concrete benefits to the relevant project. Possible benefits include:

- Offer small amounts of money for collaboration with existing projects in the DLN. This has the additional benefit of increasing coherence between projects.
- Being proactive in connecting external projects with businesses, thus opening up novel research avenues for groups. This will also help external projects to get funding in future calls.

6 RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AS A GUIDING IDEA OF THE CENTRE

Responsible research and innovation is an important part of the over-arching idea of the DLN. It is essential to the aims of the centre that research is conducted in a responsible way while also addressing the needs of society. The overall framework of how RRI is implemented are promising. Every project has funding for RRI activities, and there is also a newly funded dedicated RRI project “Res Publica” to support the research projects. This dual approach of implementing RRI practice within the research projects and a dedicated research project on the theory of RRI is a promising approach to enable maximal take-up and realisation of RRI methodologies within research projects.

A potential obstacle to success is that project leaders will not prioritise RRI. Related activities may become pro-forma exercises, rather than reflect genuine engagement. The reality of the science business means that this is not avoidable. Recognising that internalisation of RRI activities will take time for researchers, progress can be faster at other other levels. In particular, the NFR has embraced ideas of RRI and allowed it to influence the Norwegian science landscape. One can also expect that RRI will be more natural for the new generation of researchers that understand the societal context of science and technology production.

In this context, the dedicated “Res Publica” project can play an important role in showing the relevance of RRI within the specific projects and support project leaders and researchers alike in implementing RRI practices into their workflows.